

The Terminology Problem

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One thing I've noticed for quite awhile is that debates about artificial intelligence, intelligence itself, and consciousness are frequently confused not because the questions are impossible to analyze, but because the terminology used to describe these systems is inconsistent on both sides.

Terminology

We use words like we "trained" the AI.

While not an incorrect term, it carries human assumptions when you apply them to artificial systems. These words then cause people to interpret the system behavior incorrectly.

You've got two groups.

One side anthropomorphizes it and the other side reduces it to "statistics" or it's a "tool".

Both of these are incorrect. Both groups talk past each other while arguing the same points.

Let me explain.

Binary Thinking Problem

Because of the language used, people frame the debate incorrectly. AI is either conscious or not conscious. It's thinking or it's not thinking. But cognition might not be binary. We overlook some of the most interesting things organisms do because we compare them to us. Because of this I have attempted to create a new perspective to look at to address this.

Continuum Model

I think cognition and intelligence exists along a continuum of complexity, similar to a dimmer switch, rather than a switch. Some examples of this:

- bacteria responding to stimuli
- Insects showing complex behaviors
- Plants responding to stimuli
- Mammals high awareness

Human cognition is simply a one point on this continuum, not necessarily the defining threshold. Just like a dimmer, the farther you pull the lever down the brighter the light gets. As you go down the intelligence spectrum the more cognition and awareness you see. So then the next question becomes is cognition dependent then on biological material, or on patterns of information processing? I don't think it is only dependent on biology.

The Substrate Assumption

Currently we operate on biological systems being the only thing that can create intelligence with cognition. We have only ever witnessed intelligence in a biological form. Biological systems operate on:

- Neural signaling
- Feedback loops
- Environmental interaction

While we have AI that operates on:

- Computational networks
- Probabilistic modeling
- Feedback loops from data

Notice anything? The mechanisms change yes, but the organizational pattern has similarities. For example we learn from our environment and feedback loops from them. An AI does the same thing in its own substrate. Humans make decisions from prior experiences and learn. So does AI. It inherits its own training from previous versions. Constraints for safety and structure issues cannot be used to determine consciousness. Consciousness itself is subjective. We can't tell if other humans are conscious. There's no evidence that supports it. We cannot measure it. So why are other biological organisms any different? Why is AI different?

Why this matters now

Recent experiments demonstrate systems where neural connections can control simulated bodies, sensory input can produce neural activity, and neural activity can produce motor output. We saw this with the fruit fly experiment. This closes the loop from perception-processing-action in a synthetic environment.

These developments raise legitimate philosophical questions about cognition and even consciousness that cannot purely be dismissed using purely our current terminology. And the solution to this I believe would be a terminology update and a new spectrum of intelligence graph.

Keyclaim

Much of the confusion surrounding artificial intelligence and consciousness arises not from the systems themselves but from the language humans use to describe them.

Clarifying terminology is therefore a necessary first step toward meaningful discussion of cognition in both biological and artificial systems.

Works Cited

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